

Syntheses of Methyl Ether of Anaphatol and Three Other Natural Phthalides†

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Syntheses of the methyl ether (V) of a natural phthalide anaphatol (II) (5-hydroxy-7-O-3'-methylbut-2'-enylphthalide), two other natural phthalides, viz., 5,7-dihydroxyphthalide (I) and anaphatol (II) (5-hydroxy-7-O-3'-methylbut-2'-enylphthalide) isolated from the whole plant of *Anaphalis contorta* (Asteraceae) along with 5-methoxy-7-hydroxyphthalide (III). The present communication describes the synthesis of I and two other natural phthalides, viz., 5-methoxy-7-hydroxyphthalide (III) and 5,7-dimethoxyphthalide (IV) reported from *Helichrysum arenarium*³ and the synthesis of methyl ether (V) of anaphatol and 4,6-diacetoxypthalide (VI) thus providing unambiguous support to the formulations of the natural phthalides.

EARLIER, we reported^{1,2} the structures of two new phthalides, viz., 5,7-dihydroxyphthalide (I) and anaphatol (II) (5-hydroxy-7-O-3'-methylbut-2'-enylphthalide) isolated from the whole plant of *Anaphalis contorta* (Asteraceae) along with 5-methoxy-7-hydroxyphthalide (III). The present communication describes the synthesis of I and two other natural phthalides, viz., 5-methoxy-7-hydroxyphthalide (III) and 5,7-dimethoxyphthalide (IV) reported from *Helichrysum arenarium*³ and the synthesis of methyl ether (V) of anaphatol and 4,6-diacetoxypthalide (VI) thus providing unambiguous support to the formulations of the natural phthalides.

Methyl 3,5-dihydroxy-2-formylbenzoate (VII) prepared according to the method of Birkinshaw *et al*⁴ was methylated⁵ by Me_2SO_4 and anhydrous K_2CO_3 in dry acetone to afford its dimethyl ether (VIII), m.p. 100° (yield 75%). The latter upon oxidation with KMnO_4 and MgSO_4 in aq. acetone yielded methyl 3,5-dimethoxy-2-carboxybenzoate (IX), m.p. 169° (65%) which on subsequent

reduction by LiAlH_4 in dry ether gave 5,7-dimethoxyphthalide (IV), m.p. 146°, in 60% yield. Synthesis of compound (IV) by a different route was reported⁶ recently. Compound (IV) underwent demethylation with BBr_3 in dry CH_2Cl_2 to form 5,7-dihydroxyphthalide (I) in poor yield (38%). Both the synthetic phthalides (I) and (IV) were found to be identical in all respects with the corresponding natural ones.

Treatment of IV with anhydrous AlCl_3 in dry CH_2Cl_2 effected regioselective demethylation⁷ of 7-OMe to furnish 5-methoxy-7-hydroxyphthalide (III), m.p. 180°, in 60% yield, identical in all respects with the corresponding natural phthalide. Again, 5-methoxy-7-hydroxyphthalide (III) was condensed with γ,γ -dimethylallyl bromide (X) in dry acetone and anhydrous K_2CO_3 to produce anaphatol methyl ether (V) in 56% yield. Compound (V) on mild treatment with anhydrous AlCl_3 in dry ether (r.t., 48 hr) underwent preferential dealylation¹ at the allylic site to afford compound (III). Thus V could not be converted to anaphatol

† Dedicated to Prof. J. N. Mukherjee on the occasion of his 90th birthday.

(II). Compound (X) was obtained from methyl β,β -dimethylacrylate (XI) through its LiAlH_4 reduction⁹ to γ,γ -dimethylallyl alcohol (XII) followed by treatment⁹ with 48% HBr and conc. H_2SO_4 .

On the other hand, compound (VII) was hydrolysed to the corresponding acid (XIII) which was reduced by NaBH_4 in dry methanol to afford a gummy mass containing 4,6-dihydroxyphthalide formed during the work-up by cyclisation of the intermediate 3,5-dihydroxy-2-hydroxymethylbenzoic acid. Acetylation of the above gummy product afforded 4,6-diacetoxypthalide in 50% yield.

Experimental

Methyl 3,5-dimethoxy-2-carboxy benzoate (IX): Methyl 3,5-dihydroxy-2-formyl benzoate (VII), prepared⁴ from α -resorcylic acid, was methylated with Me_2SO_4 and anhydrous K_2CO_3 in dry acetone in the usual way to yield methyl 3,5-dimethoxy-2-formylbenzoate (VIII), m.p. 100° , in 75% yield. A solution of KMnO_4 (1.5 g; 0.01 mole) and anhydrous MgSO_4 (1.1 g; 0.01 mole) in water (20 ml) was added slowly to a solution of VIII (1 g; 0.0045 mole) in acetone (20 ml). The mixture was refluxed on water bath for ~ 1 hr when the colour of KMnO_4 was discharged. The mixture was cooled, acidified with dil. HCl and then solid NaHSO_3 was added pinchwise until all the MnO_2 was dissolved. The product was extracted with ether and the ether layer dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Removal of the solvent followed by crystallisation from petrol⁹ furnished compound (IX) (650 mg, m.p. 169° (yield 65%) $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$ (M^+ 240); ir (KBr): 1600(s), 1700(s), 1725(s), 3250-3400(b) cm^{-1} ; MS: peaks at m/z 240 (M^+ , 28%), 223 ($M^+ - \text{OH}$, 22%), 210 ($M^+ - \text{CH}_2\text{O}$, 7%), 209 ($M^+ - \text{OCH}_3$, 35%), 208 (m/z 223 - CH_3 , 82%), 165 (m/z 210 - CO_2H , 35%), 164 (m/z 223 - CO_2Me , 100%), 135 (m/z 165 - CH_2O , 52%), 134 (m/z 165 - OCH_3 , 55%), 107 (m/z 135 - CO, 22%), 106 (m/z 134 - CO, 97%).

5,7-Dimethoxyphthalide (IV): To a stirred slurry of LiAlH_4 (~ 80 mg; ~ 0.002 mole) in dry ether (50 ml) was added dropwise a solution of compound (IX) (0.5 g; 0.002 mole) in dry ether (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. After cooling 6N H_2SO_4 (10 ml) was added slowly. The mixture was then refluxed for another 1 hr, cooled and the ether layer was washed, dried and evaporated to yield a gummy mass. The latter was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with ethyl acetate-petrol (4:6) afforded a colourless solid (210 mg) crystallising from chloroform-petrol to 5,7-dimethoxyphthalide (IV) in colourless needles, m.p. 146° (yield 60%). The compound was found to be identical in all respect (m.m.p., co-tlc, ir) with the natural 5,7-dimethoxyphthalide

5,7-Dihydroxyphthalide (I): 5,7-Dimethoxyphthalide (IV) (20 mg) was treated with BBR_3 in dry CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml, r.t., 28 hr). Water (5 ml) was added to the residue obtained by removal of

solvent in *vacuo*. The mixture was heated on water bath for 0.5 hr, cooled and extracted with ether. Evaporation afforded a residue which upon chromatography over silica gel (100-200 mesh) gave 5,7-dihydroxyphthalide (I), 6.5 mg, (yield 38%), m.p. 240° , identical (m.m.p., ir, co-tlc) with the corresponding natural phthalide.

5-Methoxy-7-hydroxyphthalide (III): To a stirred suspension of anhydrous AlCl_3 (~ 220 mg; ~ 0.0016 mole) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml) was added 5,7-dimethoxyphthalide (IV) (150 mg; 0.0008 mole) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml), and the resulting mixture was refluxed for 1.5 hr followed by another 0.5 hr after addition of dil. HCl (5 ml). The residue obtained after removal of CH_2Cl_2 in *vacuo* was triturated with water and then extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated to yield a gummy mass which upon chromatography afforded from ethyl acetate-petrol (1:1) eluates 5-methoxy-7-hydroxyphthalide (III), 84 mg, (yield 60%), m.p. 180° , identical (m.m.p., ir, co-tlc) with the corresponding natural phthalide.

γ,γ -Dimethylallyl alcohol (XII): Methyl β,β -dimethylacrylate (XI) (20 ml) was reduced⁹ by LiAlH_4 in dry ether giving γ,γ -dimethylallyl alcohol (XII), (13 ml), b.p. 145° . PMR (CDCl_3 , 80 MHz): δ 1.82 and 1.88 [3H, s each, $=\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$], 2.47 (1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , OH group), 4.00 (2H, d, $J=7\text{Hz}$, CH_2OH), 5.30 (1H, t, $J=7\text{Hz}$, $=\text{CH}$).

γ,γ -Dimethylallyl bromide (X): Treatment of compound (XII) (10 ml) with 48% HBr and conc. H_2SO_4 afforded γ,γ -dimethylallyl bromide (X), (5 ml), b.p. 135° .

Anaphatol methyl ether (V): A mixture of 5-methoxy-7-hydroxyphthalide (III) (50 mg), the liquid bromide (X) (0.1 ml), dry acetone (20 ml) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (150 mg) was refluxed for 16 hr, cooled, diluted with excess acetone and filtered. Evaporation of the filtrate and crystallisation of the residue with petrol afforded anaphatol methyl ether (V), 45 mg, (yield 56%), m.p. 110° . PMR (CDCl_3 , 80 MHz): δ 1.73 [6H, s, 3'-(CH_3)₂], 3.83 (3H, s, 5-OCH₃), 4.66 (2H, d, $J=6.4\text{Hz}$, H_2-1'), 5.11 (2H, s, H_2-3), 5.47 (1H, t, $J=6.5\text{Hz}$, $\text{H}-2'$), 6.38 and 6.42 (1H, bs, each, H-6 and H-4, respectively). Compound (V) is identical (m.m.p., ir, co-tlc) with the methyl ether of the naturally occurring phthalide anaphatol¹.

4,6-Diacetoxypthalide (VI): Methyl 3,5-dihydroxy-2-formyl benzoate (VII) (150 mg) was hydrolysed by dil. NaOH and the product (XIII) (100 mg) reduced by NaBH_4 in dry MeOH. Extraction with ether after usual decomposition of the complex by dil. HCl yielded a gummy mass, which on acetylation gave 4,6-diacetoxypthalide (VI), 70 mg, (yield 50%), m.p. 122° . PMR (CDCl_3 , 80 MHz): δ 2.36 (6H, s, two phenolic OCOCH_3), 5.24 (2H, s, H_2-3), 7.29 (1H, bs, H-5), 7.57 (1H, bs, H-7).

* b.p. $60-80^\circ$.

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